

Atmospheric turbulence characterization at AlUla Manara Observatory in Saudi Arabia: early results from SHIMM operations

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ABSTRACT

The AlUla Manara Observatory is being developed by the Royal Commission for AlUla in north-western Saudi Arabia as the country's first research-grade astronomical facility. Located on a remote desert plateau at ~1209 m elevation and within an International Dark Sky Park established in 2024, the site is planned to host a 4m-class optical-IR telescope.

A comprehensive site characterization campaign began in April 2025 with the deployment of an Astronomical Site Monitor (ASM). Its core instrument, a 24-hour Shack-Hartmann Image Motion Monitor (24hSHIMM), provides continuous measurements of atmospheric turbulence and estimates of its vertical distribution. Additional instrumentation includes an RPG-HATPRO radiometer for precipitable water vapor (PWV), aerosol sensors, and meteorological stations for vertical microclimate characterization.

This work presents the first results from SHIMM operations, analyzing the temporal behavior and vertical structure of atmospheric turbulence under desert conditions and early assessment of the site's suitability for adaptive optics assisted observations.

Keywords: site testing, atmospheric turbulence, turbulence profiling, atmospheric effects

1. INTRODUCTION

The AlUla Manara Observatory is being developed in north-western Saudi Arabia by the Royal Commission for AlUla (RCU). The proposed site is located on a rocky desert plateau at an elevation of approximately 1209 m above sea level [1; 2], about 74 km north of the town of AlUla in the Medinah Province (see Table 1 and Figure 1). In 2024 the area was designated an International Dark Sky Park [3], with a further extension in 2025, reflecting the low levels of artificial light and the commitment to preserve the natural night sky of the region. The project is intended to establish Saudi Arabia's first research-grade astronomical observatory.

The current concept foresees the installation of a 4m-class optical-IR telescope together with two robotic telescopes of approximately 2m-class aperture. The facility is planned to support both scientific research and educational activities, while also contributing to the development of astro-tourism in the AlUla region. At the time of writing, the observatory infrastructure and telescope systems are in the early stages of conceptual design, and the technical specifications of the instruments are under definition.

As part of the preparatory work for the observatory, a dedicated site characterization campaign was initiated to evaluate the atmospheric and environmental conditions of the plateau. An Astronomical Site Monitor (ASM) was deployed at the site and began operations in April 2025 [1; 2]. The ASM includes several instruments designed to measure key parameters relevant for optical and infrared observations.

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Table 1. AIUla Manara astronomical site geographical and regional information.

ALULA MANARA OBSERVATORY			
<u>Geographical information</u>		<u>Regional information</u>	
Latitude	27° 11' 32.4" N	Country	Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Longitude	37° 48' 40.1" E	Province	Medinah
Elevation	1209 m	Closest town	AIUla

Figure 1. Geographical position of the AIUla Manara astronomical site in western Saudi Arabia.

To our knowledge, no previous long-term turbulence monitoring campaigns have been reported for astronomical site characterization within the Cooperation Council for the Arab States of the Gulf (GCC) region. This work therefore represents one of the first efforts to systematically characterize a potential astronomical site in the area.

A central component of the monitoring system is a 24-hour Shack-Hartmann Image Motion Monitor (24hSHIMM), which operates continuously and provides measurements of atmospheric turbulence and seeing conditions during both daytime and nighttime. These observations are complemented by additional instrumentation, including an RPG-HATPRO radiometer for measurements of precipitable water vapor (PWV), aerosol sensors for dust monitoring, and a network of meteorological sensors distributed at different heights to characterize the local microclimate.

This manuscript presents the early results obtained during the initial months of 24hSHIMM operations. The analysis focuses on the temporal behavior of atmospheric turbulence, the statistical distribution of seeing, and the relative contributions of different atmospheric layers. Particular attention is given to the performance of the monitoring system under the environmental conditions of the AIUla Manara desert plateau. These early measurements provide an initial assessment of the atmospheric properties of the site and contribute to the ongoing definition of the technical requirements for the future observatory.

RCU is also pursuing collaborations with international research institutions as part of the broader effort to develop the observatory and to establish a long-term scientific program for the site.

2. ASTRONOMICAL SITE MONITOR

Figure 2 shows the AIUla Manara Astronomical Site Monitor in daytime (left) and nighttime (right). The ASM has been designed following the process implemented for the Extremely Large Telescopes site characterization campaigns [4; 5; 6]. The ASM started operations during April 2025, and is composed by the following instrumentation:

- *Turbulence characterization.* The 24hSHIMM [7; 8; 9; 10] has been preferred to a classical Differential Image Motion Monitor (DIMM; [6; 11]) due to its ability to operate both in daytime and nighttime.

Figure 2. (left) Instrumentation at the AIUla Manara Astronomical Site Monitor. (right) AIUla Manara ASM at night.

- *Atmospheric parameters.* A 30m weather tower equipped with Automated Weather Stations (AWS) provides local and vertical microclimate analysis (wind, temperature, humidity, pressure, precipitation) at 2, 10, 20 and 30m above surface.
 - 2 m, to monitor the ground conditions;
 - 10 m, to monitor the conditions at the same level of the 24hSHIMM;
 - 20 m, to monitor the conditions at an intermediate elevation;
 - 30 m, to monitor the conditions close to the (expected) altitude of the 4m-class telescope dome.
- *Dust monitoring.* Given the desertic nature of the AIUla region, the evaluation of the dust and aerosols suspended in the atmosphere is carried out using a Met One Instruments MODEL 212 Profiler installed on the weather tower at 30m above ground.
- *Radiometer.* An RPG-HATPRO radiometer is integrated in the ASM to monitor the PWV.

A satellite link allows connectivity for data access, remote operations and troubleshooting. Power is supplied by an array of solar panels (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Solar panels and satellite link at the AIUla Manara ASM.

Figure 4. The 24hSHIMM operating at AlUla Manara. The telescope is covered with material able to dissipate heat; when not in operation, the dome interior is cooled down with an air conditioning system.

3. THE 24-HOUR SHACK-HARTMANN IMAGE MOTION MONITOR

The 24hSHIMM has been commissioned by the UK based company Lumi Space at the end of April 2025. It operates continuously during the day and the night and provides estimates of seeing, isoplanatic angle, coherence time, and Rytov variance using a four-layer vertical turbulence profile and a wind speed profile obtained from meteorological forecasts.

The instrument is mounted at the focus of an 11-inch Schmidt Cassegrain telescope, supported by a Planewave L-350 Direct Drive Alt-Az mount (Figure 4). To minimize the effects of surface layer turbulence, it has been elevated on an 8m tower (Figure 2, left), thus its final elevation is of 10m above surface. The instrument is protected by a 2.7m Pulsar dome.

The instrument operates robotically: a supervisor software is linked to the temperature, wind speed, and relative humidity sensors at 10m, with complementary information from the dust sensor at 30m and an all-sky camera installed on the 8m tower. When safety conditions are met, the 2.7m Pulsar dome is opened and operations performed, ideally, on a continuous 24h cycle.

4. ENVIRONMENTAL AND TECHNICAL CHALLENGES

The beginning of operations coincided with the warm season in Saudi Arabia (April-September), when daytime temperatures frequently exceed 40°C. These conditions represent a demanding environment for both site-testing instruments and supporting infrastructure. During the monitoring period considered in this early report, the average air temperature measured at 10m above ground level has remained relatively stable between daytime and nighttime, typically ranging between 27°C and 30°C (see Figure 5).

Given the extreme operational temperatures and expected significant day/night thermal gradients at the site, careful consideration has been given to the 24hSHIMM cooling and thermal management. The telescope is covered with material able to dissipate heat. Furthermore, the instrument is housed within a dome equipped with an air-conditioning system used to reduce internal temperatures when the instrument is not observing. During measurements the cooling system is switched off in order to prevent turbulence inside the dome, which could otherwise affect the seeing measurements. We expect residual dome seeing to dissipate in the time span between the stop of the air conditioning system, the dome opening and start of operations.

Figure 5. Temperature distribution at 10m above surface at AIUla Manara in the period April-September 2025.

Figure 6. Wind speed distribution at 10m above surface at AIUla Manara in the period April-September 2025.

The SHIMM is installed on an 8m tower that provides the required elevation above the local surface layer but also introduces sensitivity to mechanical vibrations. Tests conducted during the first months of operation show that vibrations become significant at wind speeds above approximately 8 m/s, preventing reliable observations. Wind conditions at AIUla Manara have generally been moderate, with average wind speeds of about 4 m/s during the monitored months and only occasional gusts reaching 15 m/s. In practice, wind speeds remain below the operational threshold for approximately 95% of the time (see Figure 6), allowing regular operation of the instrument.

The terrain at the site is composed mainly of exposed rock mixed with loose sand. Under certain meteorological conditions, particularly during north-westerly wind events, this environment can give rise to sudden dust storms (Figure 7). While such events have not posed a direct risk to the current ASM campaign, they highlight an environmental factor that will need to be considered in the operational planning of the future observatory. Appropriate mitigation strategies, including protective procedures and operational constraints during dust events, will likely be required.

Figure 7. Example of dust storm events at AIUla Manara between 10 and 19 May 2025.

Figure 8. The path to AIUla Manara that originates from route 375 in the Medinah Province.

Logistical aspects also represent an important challenge for the site operations. The location is remote and currently lacks telephone connectivity. Access to the monitoring station is provided by an unpaved track crossing rocky and sandy terrain (Figure 8), which makes travel to the site slow and sometimes difficult. As a consequence, maintenance interventions and inspections require careful planning and involve significant logistical effort, including transportation, safety considerations, and personnel coordination.

At present, communication with the site relies on a satellite internet link. The available bandwidth is limited and the connection can be unstable, which complicates remote operations and troubleshooting activities. As a result, tasks that would normally be performed quickly through remote access may require extended time and additional on-site intervention.

Figure 9. Diurnal trend of the Fried parameter at AIUla Manara (April-September 2025).

5. PRELIMINARY ALULA MANARA TURBULENCE CHARACTERIZATION

In Figure 9 we show that during the semester April-September 2025, at AIUla Manara the Fried parameter (r_0) exhibits a nearly constant trend throughout the nighttime hours. As expected, during daytime, a progressive decrease in r_0 is observed, reaching its minimum near the time of maximum solar elevation. Notably, the standard deviation of r_0 is significantly lower during the daytime. We confirmed that this reduction in variability is not attributable to an uneven temporal sampling across the 24-hour period, suggesting that the effect could be physical rather than a statistical artifact. It indicates that r_0 values are more consistent across different days at the same time, despite the overall daytime degradation in seeing.

Figure 10 shows that the measured median seeing during nighttime is approximately 1.1-1.2 arcsec. During daytime the seeing degrades, with a median value above ~ 2.0 arcsec, although the overall conditions remain compatible with solar observations.

As shown in Figure 11, the atmospheric coherence time during the night is estimated to be ~ 4.2 msec, decreasing to ~ 3.1 msec during daytime. The isoplanatic angle is measured at ~ 1.8 arcsec at night and ~ 1.4 arcsec during daytime.

These preliminary values indicate atmospheric conditions that are compatible with the implementation of adaptive optics systems, although longer monitoring is required to fully characterize the turbulence statistics of the site.

Figure 10. Seeing cumulative distribution at AIUla Manara (April-September 2025).

Figure 11. Coherence time cumulative distribution at AIUla Manara (April-September 2025).

Figure 12. Isoplanatic angle cumulative distribution at AIUla Manara (April-September 2025).

Table 2. Relative contribution of individual atmospheric layers in percentage [%] of the total C_n^2 for good (25%), median (50%) and bad (75%) seeing conditions at AIUla Manara (April-September 2025).

	DAYTIME				NIGHTTIME			
	0 km	4 km	12 km	20 km	0 km	4 km	12 km	20 km
GOOD (25%)	67.9	27.7	3.0	1.4	64.9	24.2	8.9	2.0
MEDIAN (50%)	85.9	13.0	0.5	0.6	68.9	22.4	7.1	1.6
BAD (75%)	93.5	5.7	0.3	0.5	82.2	15.9	1.4	0.5

Figure 13. C_n^2 profiles for good (25%), median (50%) and bad (75%) seeing conditions at AIUla Manara in daytime and nighttime (April-September 2025).

The median turbulence profiles for daytime and nighttime conditions are shown in Figure 13, while Table 2 reports the relative contribution of individual atmospheric layers as a percentage of the total integrated C_n^2 . During nighttime, the first few kilometers above the surface contribute between $\sim 60\%$ and $\sim 80\%$ of the total turbulence strength. During daytime this fraction increases, ranging between $\sim 70\%$ and more than 90% . These results indicate that a significant fraction of the turbulence is concentrated in the lower atmosphere. Given the current results, the use of a complementary high-vertical-resolution turbulence profiler would help to better characterize the distribution of turbulence within the first kilometers above the ground.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents the first months of atmospheric turbulence measurements obtained with the Astronomical Site Monitor deployed at the AIUla Manara Observatory site in Saudi Arabia. The monitoring campaign began in April 2025 and represents one of the first systematic efforts to characterize atmospheric turbulence for astronomical applications in the GCC region.

The preliminary results indicate a median nighttime seeing of approximately 1.1-1.2 arcsec, while daytime seeing degrades to values above ~ 2.0 arcsec. The atmospheric coherence time is estimated at ~ 4.2 msec during the night and ~ 3.1 msec during daytime, while the isoplanatic angle shows median values of ~ 1.8 arcsec at night and ~ 1.4 arcsec during the day. These measurements suggest atmospheric conditions that are compatible with adaptive optics assisted observations, although longer-term monitoring will be required to establish robust seasonal statistics.

The turbulence profile analysis indicates that a significant fraction of the optical turbulence is concentrated in the lower atmosphere. During nighttime the first kilometers above the surface account for roughly 60-80% of the total turbulence strength, while during daytime this contribution increases to values between $\sim 70\%$ and $>90\%$.

The campaign has also demonstrated that continuous turbulence monitoring can be successfully conducted under the environmental conditions of the AIUla desert plateau. Despite high daytime temperatures, dust events, and logistical constraints related to the remote location, the ASM infrastructure has proven capable of operating reliably.

The continuation of the monitoring campaign will allow the collection of a longer dataset covering additional seasons, which will be essential for refining the turbulence statistics and for supporting the technical definition of the future AIUla Manara Observatory.

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